

IST&I
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE
TECHNOLOGY & INNOVATION

UM6P-CS
SCHOOL OF
COMPUTER SCIENCE

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TITLE OF THE INTERNSHIP SUBJECT

***Network Packet level –based Intelligent
Phishing Intrusion Detection System
(NIPDS)***

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UM6P-CS: School of computer Science

Protractors of my internship work: Prof. Ahmed RATNANI and Prof. Achraf EL ALLALI

Academic year: 2021-2022

Realized by

Khaoula Hidawi

Supervised by

Dr. Ismail Berrada

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A. Introduction

I. The Research Problem

The Internet has become an indispensable component of our daily social and financial lives. Nonetheless, internet users may be subject to a variety of web threats that can result in financial losses, identity theft, data loss, and brand reputation damage be it the public or private sectors. Phishing is a type of web threat and cybercrime defined as the act of imitating a legitimate company's website in order to steal sensitive information such as usernames, passwords, and social security numbers.

Figure 1- Most Target Industries in Phishing Cyber-attacks [5]

So far, there is no single solution that can capture every phishing attack at a network-based level for real HTTPS data flow, According to a report [1] by the Anti-Phishing Working Group (APWG) and contributor Phish Labs, in the first quarter of 2021, 83% of phishing sites had SSL encryption enabled. In this study, we introduced a unique intelligent models for predicting phishing attacks. Network-based intrusion detection systems that monitor cutting-edge high-volume network linkages need greater computing resources than ordinary computer hardware can provide. Possible use cases for merging traditional, packet-based, and innovative, flow-based intrusion detection

are described using this model. An increasing amount of web traffic is currently encrypted using HTTPS. While most of the HTTPS traffic is legitimate, a growing slice is generated by malware. The use of the HTTPS protocol by malware and phishing attacks makes its detection more challenging.

Figure 2- HTTPS Phishing by Year [5]

The current strategy in the literature is to use HTTPS interceptor proxies to identify HTTPS malware traffic [4]. This technology necessitates on-the-fly decryption of traffic, which poses certain risks to data and communication security and privacy.

```

Remote Address: 93.184.216.34:80
Request URL: http://www.example.com/?latitude=45.000&longitude=-90.000
Request Method: GET
Status Code: 200 OK
▼ Request Headers
Accept-Language: en-US,en;q=0.8
User-Agent: Mozilla/5.0 (X11; Linux x86_64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/40.0.2214.91 Safari/537.36
Cookie: __utma=176327073.955859883.1419291030.1419291030.1421608763.2; __utmz=176327073.1419291030.1.1.utmcsr=(direct)
▼ Query String Parameters
latitude: 45.000
longitude: -90.000
    
```

Figure 3- Data shown in HTTP requested Header

Figure 4- Data shown in HTTPS header. The HTTP Urls shows the full path but in real data flow encrypted HTTPS request protects most things: This is the same for all HTTP methods (GET, POST, PUT, etc.). The URL path and query string parameters are encrypted, as are POST bodies. **We can only view domain names.**

The purpose by the end of this research project is to detect HTTPS/HTTP malicious phishing traffic without decryption by analyzing real-time device traffic and large network captures in the form of a PCAP file to extract network traffic characteristics. We propose a novel detection model that makes use of the underlying DNS traffic features that is put into a machine learning classifier. A solid feature engineering mechanism plays a pivotal role in boosting the performance of any machine learning model. Therefore, we have extracted effective and practical features from DNS traffic categorizing them into groups of lexical-based and third-party based features. Third-party features are biographical information about a specific domain extracted from third-party APIs. [2] [3]. Experimental evaluation is conducted using a CSV public dataset that we preprocessed and generated while the model training data is taken from CIC-Bell-DNS 2021 Dataset, which is a collaborative project with Bell Canada (BC) and Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) [18]. In their work, they generated and released a large DNS features dataset of 400,000 benign and 13,011 malicious samples processed from a million benign and 51,453 known-malicious domains from publicly available datasets. The malicious samples span between three categories of spam, phishing, and malware - For our research project I only worked with the phishing samples. The CIC-Bell-DNS2021 was the best decision for this research because it replicates the real-world scenarios with frequent benign traffic and malicious domain types [18].

Keywords:

Web threats, HTTPS Phishing attack, HTTP/HTTPS protocol, Information security, neural network, Data mining, Network-based IDS, encrypted Network traffic, Cyber Threat intelligence, Machine learning ,DNS traffic.

II. Planned Research Methodology

Figure 5- Phishing Attack Graph

The study methodology outlines the steps we took to try to achieve our goal of implementing a Packet-Based Intelligent Network phishing Intrusion Detection system (INPDS).

The plan includes the processes and methods we followed, as well as materials relating to the topic to be investigated.

The research problem - The first and most important stage in the research process is to define the research topic.

Review of Related Literature – This is necessary to familiarize oneself with existing research materials linked to the research problem which is identification of phishing attacks in

Networks packet-based IDS. The review for the most important intelligent models in phishing classification can be view in Section B (this step took approximately one month period).

Preparing of research design – The research design is the theoretical framework within which the research will be carried out. It serves as a guide for the gathering of data, in our instance of implementing a Packet-Based Intelligent Network phishing Intrusion Detection system. The idea of the design is to use machine learning to classify Network packets to benign and phishing in real-time flow (for both http/https protocol) based on DNS records and domain name features. It operates by using a pre-programmed list of known phishing threat features and their indicators of compromise (IOCs). As a signature based INPDS it will monitor the packets traversing the network, it compares these packets to the database of known IOCs or attack signatures to flag any suspicious behavior. (This step took approximately a month and a half).

Collection of data – After formulating the research problem, developing a research design and identifying the methods and procedures to be used, the next step was collecting sufficient data from which we can draw conclusions and inferences for the study (This step took a month to find the right training set and generating the test datasets).

Analysis of data – This involves processing and analyzing the collected data then organizing it in a manner where the information can answer the question or give solution to decreasing phishing attacks in real time flow using machine learning models.

Generalization – Here, we puts the summary of all the findings of the research. Recommendations was also be included in this section of the research methodology.

Presentation of results – The research will then be presented to a panel to defend the relevance of the study conducted by contrast to exciting phishing classification models.

B. State of the Art: Review of Related Literature

The following figure lists the experimental results of some existing models on detecting phishing attacks in the literature. For the generality of comparisons, four kinds of phishing detection methods were selected in the experiment, including the phishing detection system proposed by Ma (abbreviated as “Ma” in this table) based on the blacklist; the Cantina model

based on the heuristic method; the tool proposed by Zhang (abbreviated as “Zhang” in this table) based on the visual similarity method; the Off the-Hook with the results being the averages often repetitive experiments on the two datasets. We can see that, due to strong learning ability and high classification accuracy, the performances of neural network classifiers (ANN and DTOF-ANN) are better than the other classifiers in the literature, in this section I reviewed the best-classified models for phishing detection, their limitations, implementations, and findings:

Table 7
Performance comparisons between DTOF-ANN and some classical classifiers.

Classifiers	Precision	Recall	F1_score	Accuracy
NB	0.5189	0.9979	0.6828	0.5970
LR	0.9313	0.9022	0.9165	0.9285
GBDT	0.9573	0.9324	0.9447	0.9525
SVM	0.9601	0.9261	0.9420	0.9512
ANN	0.9653	0.9563	0.9563	0.9661
RF	0.9688	0.9620	0.9654	0.9688
DT	0.9460	0.9640	0.9549	0.9588
DTOF-ANN	0.9776	0.9736	0.9761	0.9780

Table 8
Performance comparisons between DTOF-ANN and some existing methods.

Models	Datasets		Precision	Recall	F1_score	Accuracy
	Legal	Phishing				
Ma	15000	20500	0.9980	0.9240	0.9510	0.9550
Cantina	2100	19	0.2120	0.8920	0.3420	0.9690
Zhang	100	100	0.9100	0.9792	0.9150	0.9150
Off-the-Hook	20000	2000	0.9750	0.9510	0.9630	0.9990
Cantina+	1868	940	0.9640	0.9640	0.9640	0.9550
DTOF-ANN	18004	7633	0.9776	0.9736	0.9761	0.9780

Figure 6- Classical Phishing Models

Research Article	Problem Addressed / Identified	Research Contribution	Novelty/Rationale and Significance:	Limitations and Weaknesses	Implementation Details	Findings and Conclusions
<p>URLNet: Learning a URL Representation with Deep Learning for Malicious URL Detection [6]</p>	<p>Malicious URLs host unsolicited content and are used to perpetrate cybercrime traditionally, this is done through the usage of blacklists, which cannot be exhaustive, and cannot detect newly generated malicious URLs. To address this, recent years have witnessed several efforts to perform Malicious URL Detection using Machine Learning. The most popular and scalable approaches use lexical properties of the URL string by extracting Bag-of-words like features, followed by applying machine learning models such as SVMs. There are also other features designed by experts to improve the prediction performance of the model. These approaches suffer from several limitations: (i) Inability to effectively capture semantic</p>	<p>To address these challenges, the researchers propose URLNet, an end-to-end deep learning framework to learn a nonlinear URL embedding for Malicious URL Detection directly from the URL. Specifically, they apply Convolutional Neural Networks to both characters and words of the URL String to learn the URL embedding in a jointly optimized framework.</p>	<p>URLNet allows us to alleviate the shortcomings of traditional approaches such that Character and Word CNNs automatically identify and learn the semantic and sequential patterns in which the characters and words appear in the URL; as well as automatically learns features to represent the URL, and we do not rely on any other complex or expert features for the learning task; and also The model learns patterns based on both character and word embedding. Due</p>	<p>In this research the authors focused primarily on the lexical features to obtain the feature representation for the URLs. The most popular features were Bag of Words, Term Frequency features or n-gram features. However, the authors argue that none of these</p>	<p>The model comprises two branches with CNNs. The first branch is a Character-level CNN where the character embedding is used to represent the URL. The second is the Word-level CNN where a word-level embedding is used to represent the URL. The word embedding itself is a combination of the individual word's embedding and the character-level embedding of that word.</p>	<p>The article proposed Character CNNs and Word CNNs for this task, and jointly optimized the network. + they proposed advanced word-embedding techniques which are particularly useful to deal with rare words, a problem usually observed in malicious URL Detection tasks (and not in traditional NLP tasks)+ This approach also allowed URLNet to learn embedding from unseen words at test time, and exploit sub word information.</p>

	<p>meaning and sequential patterns in URL strings; (ii) Requiring substantial manual feature engineering; and (iii) Inability to handle unseen features and generalize to test data.</p>		<p>to the limited number of characters, this character embedding can generalize to new URLs easily. For word-embedding, even if the test URLs contain new unseen words, the character-based (advanced word) embedding of the words still allows us to obtain representation for these new words. This way URLNet has superior generalization ability compared to existing approaches</p>	<p>methods effectively capture the sequential properties of the URL string (or substrings). Moreover these methods fail to extract useful information from unseen words in the test URLs.</p>	<p>Dataset Collection. They collected a large corpus of labeled URLs from VirusTotal an antivirus group whose services are often used to validate whether a given query URL is malicious or not.</p>	
<p>CANTINA+: A Feature-rich Machine Learning Framework for Detecting Phishing Web Sites [7]</p>	<p>Typically, phishing detection methods either use human verified URL blacklists or exploit webpage features via machine learning techniques. However, the former is frail in terms of new phish, and the latter suffers from the scarcity of effective features and the high false positive rate (FP).</p>	<p>To alleviate those problems, The authors propose a layered anti-phishing solution that aims at 1) exploiting the expressiveness of a rich set of features with</p>	<p>An ideal anti-phishing solution needs to have reasonable TP against new attacks with very low FP while involving minimum manual labor. The key to achieve a high TP is to design new features that are characteristic</p>	<p>Cross site scripting (XSS) is a type of typical security vulnerability in web applications by which</p>	<p>In the training stage, 15 feature values are extracted from each instance in the training corpus; the feature values are organized in proper format and</p>	<p>in the randomized evaluation where training and testing phish are randomly selected, CANTINA+ achieved over 92% TP on unique testing phish, over 99% TP on near-duplicate testing phish, and about 0.4%</p>

		<p><i>machine learning to achieve a high true positive rate (TP) on novel phish, and 2) limiting the FP to a low level via filtering algorithms. Specifically, the article proposed CANTINA+, a comprehensive feature-based approach in the literature including eight novel features, which exploits the HTML Document Object Model (DOM), search engines and third party services with machine learning techniques to detect phishing.</i></p>	<p><i>of phishing patterns, and the core ingredient leading to a very low FP is filtering via heuristics. With those in mind, + this research goal in this paper is contributing to the literature by addressing the weaknesses of both blacklists and feature-based methods in a unified framework. By proposing novel features to improve the TP and design filtering algorithms absent in the literature to reduce FP and human effort.</i></p>	<p><i>criminals may launch a variant of phishing attack. This anti-phishing solution is certainly not a panacea, but it is not designed to deal with this type of attacks in the first place. In this case, the authors suggest that they will rely on other techniques such as cookie protection to assist our approach in detecting phish.</i></p>	<p><i>forwarded to the ML engine; Then classifiers are built for phish detection. In the testing stage, the hash-based filter examines whether or not the incoming page is a near duplicate of known phish based on comparing SHA1 hashes; if no hash match is found, the login form detector is called, which directly classifies the webpage as legitimate if no login form is identified; the webpage is sent to the feature extractor when a login form is detected;</i></p>	<p><i>FP under 10% training phish with login form filtering to slash false positives. In the time-based evaluation methodology where earlier phish were used as training data to build classification models for later attacks, the approach achieved over 92% TP on unique testing phish, over 99% TP on near-duplicate testing phish, and about 1.4% FP under 20% training phish with a two-week sliding window.</i></p>
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<p>Cat BERT: Context-Aware Tiny BERT for Detecting Targeted Social Engineering Email [8]</p>	<p>Social engineering attacks leveraging hand-crafted emails are a major threat vector today. Because these emails are often hand-written, individually targeted, and incorporate background research on their targets, they pose a significant challenge for conventional detection systems which reply on spam-like duplication between previously seen and new malicious emails.</p>	<p><i>To address the challenges, the paper propose a phishing detection strategy based on transformers , leveraging a BERT-derived approach that is trained on a self-supervised cloze task on a public corpus of documents and then optimizing the language model to perform phishing detection. This transfer-learning procedure allows the network to learn a useful representation of natural language syntax and semantics before specialization in phishing detection.</i></p>	<p><i>Model leverages both natural language and email header inputs, is more computationally efficient than competing transformer approaches, plus it is less prone to adversarial attacks which deliberately replace keywords with typos or synonyms.</i></p>	<p><i>Distil-BERT has 135 million parameters, which is the largest model with 6 Transformer blocks, and a correspondingly long inference time. Cat-BERT with 3 Transformer blocks has 117 million parameters, is about 15% smaller than Distil-BERT and obtains 1.6x speed up in CPU inference time (using an AWS m5.large instance</i></p>	<p><i>The proposed Cat-BERT model is downsized from Distil-BERT by taking odd-numbered Transformers and replacing missing Transformers with simple Adapters, which we find reduces model size with no cost to accuracy. The adapters consists of two dense and a ReLU activation units with a residual connection. The content input from email text is fed to the Embedding block and the context input from email headers is combined in the classification head in Cat-BERT.</i></p>	<p><i>They conducted experiments with two non-BERT models, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Logistic Regression (LR). Also baselined with Distil-BERT, trained with Adam and with a class-balanced batch size of 128. Cat-BERT, proposed model, has three Transformer blocks with content and context features. As seen from figure 2. It outperform all the other models.</i></p>
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				<p><i>type). The relatively modest reduction in parameter size for Cat BERT is due to the fact that all three models use a large embedding layer with 92 million parameters, which accounts for about 70% of all parameters.</i></p>		
<p><i>DTOF-ANN: An Artificial Neural Network phishing detection model based on Decision Tree and</i></p>	<p><i>Duplicate points in public datasets and negative and useless features in the feature vectors trap the training of neural networks into the problem of over-fitting, which will make the trained classifier weak when detect phishing websites.</i></p>	<p><i>This paper proposes DTOF-ANN (Decision Tree and Optimal Features based Artificial Neural Network) to tackle this shortcoming, which is a neural-</i></p>	<p><i>The traditional clustering algorithm is improved with an incremental selection of initial centers to remove the duplicate points from the public datasets. Plus, an optimal feature</i></p>		<p><i>The overall workflow of DTOF-ANN, which can be divided into two stages: the training stage and the testing stage. The former stage first introduces the</i></p>	<p><i>The Blacklist module improves the performance, which is constructed by selecting data points from the Alexa website and the Phish Tank website. The tested URLs are firstly checked</i></p>

<p>Optimal Features [9]</p>		<p>network phishing detection model based on decision tree and optimal feature selection.</p>	<p>selection algorithm based on the new defined feature evaluation index, decision tree and local search method is designed to prune out the negative and useless features. The optimal structure of the neural network classifier is constructed through properly adjusting parameters and trained by the selected optimal features.</p>		<p>improved K-medoids algorithm to delete the duplicate data points in the open phishing datasets. Then, the optimal feature selection algorithm is designed to construct the optimal feature vector for the underlying neural network classifier, where the new index, F value, is defined to evaluate the importance of phishing features of data points in the phishing datasets.</p>	<p>by querying if they are already existed in the Blacklist. The target URLs are directly marked as the phishing ones if so, and, otherwise, the optimal feature vectors of the corresponding URLs are processed by the trained neural network classifier. The detected phishing URLs are also stored in the Blacklist to avoid the same kinds of URL in the future processed repeatedly.</p>
<p>Off-the-Hook: An Efficient and Usable Client-Side Phishing Prevention</p>	<p>The state-of-the-art solutions in the literature have good performance, but they suffer from several drawbacks including potential to compromise user privacy, difficulty of detecting phishing websites whose content</p>	<p>To address these limitations the authors present a new approach for detecting phishing webpages in real-time as they are</p>	<p>Introducing a new phish detection tool, Off-the-Hook, implemented as a browser add-on that can decide in real time if a visited webpage is</p>	<p>The authors stated that: "The interpretation and appreciation of the safe</p>	<p>Off-the-Hook is fully implemented on the client-side. It computes its decision based on the webpage content actually</p>	<p>Preserves users' privacy, provides real-time protection and is resilient to dynamic phish since the content actually loaded in the</p>

<p>Application [10]</p>	<p><i>change dynamically, and reliance on features that are too dependent on the training data.</i></p>	<p><i>visited by a browser. Their approaches relies on modeling inherent phisher limitations stemming from the constraints they face while building a webpage ,Off-the-Hook, exhibits several notable properties including high accuracy, brand-independence and good language-independence, speed of decision, resilience to dynamic phish and resilience to evolution in phishing techniques.</i></p>	<p><i>a phish. On encountering a phish, Off-the-Hook identifies the target brand mimicked by the phish. Off-the-Hook implementation is fully-client-side and the decision process relies solely on information extracted from the web browser while loading a webpage.</i></p>	<p><i>toast notification were less clear, as some considered it redundant but others found it helpful. No user correctly guessed why it appears on some sites and not others, which is potentially problematic. Removing the safe toast notification would be a possible remedy for this, given that the same information is also</i></p>	<p><i>displayed in the browser. It is thus privacy preserving and is not vulnerable to dynamic phishes. The features used for the model are non-static: they represent phisher limitations rather than static words found in training data. The detection is thus context-independent</i></p>	<p><i>browser is analyzed to render a decision.</i></p>
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				<p><i>present at the navigation bar. The main usability problem with this would be that the loading screen may result in confusion or suspicion, since it currently has no information.</i></p>		
<p>CANTINA: A Content-Based Approach to Detecting Phishing Web [11]</p>	<p><i>Based on the evaluation conducted by the authors of ten anti-phishing tools for previous study, They found that only one tool could consistently detect more than 60% of phishing web sites without a high rate of false positives.</i></p>	<p><i>The paper present the design, implementation, and evaluation of CANTINA a novel content-based approach for detecting phishing web sites. CANTINA examines the content of a web</i></p>	<p><i>Authors argue that there is a strong need for better automated detection algorithms that reduce false positives (incorrectly labeling legitimate web sites as phishing), while lowering phish detection rates only slightly.</i></p>	<p><i>CANTINA suffers from performance problems due to the time lag involved in querying Google. Another issue is the potential for</i></p>	<p><i>CANTINA makes use of TF-IDF for detecting phishing sites. TF-IDF is a well-known information retrieval algorithm that can be used for comparing and classifying documents, as well</i></p>	<p><i>The result of the experiments shows that the pure TF-IDF approach can catch about 97% phishing sites with about 6% false positives, and after combining some simple heuristics they were able to catch about 90% of</i></p>

		<p><i>page to determine whether it is legitimate or not, in contrast to other approaches that look at surface characteristics of a web page, for example the URL and its domain name</i></p>		<p><i>attackers to circumvent CANTINA. Phishing is an arms race, with criminals continually devising new ways of tricking people. So the authors have identified three direct approaches by which CANTINA might be attacked.</i></p>	<p><i>as retrieving documents from a large corpus. TF-IDF yields a weight that measures how important a word is to a document in a corpus. The importance increases proportionally to the number of times a word appears in the document, but is offset by the frequency of the word in the corpus</i></p>	<p><i>phishing sites with only 1% false positives.</i></p>
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Figure 7 - Summary of currently used anti-phishing systems

C. Preparing of Research Design

The idea behind the Design is using machine learning to classify Network packets to benign and phishing in real-time flow based on DNS and domain name features. The initial thought is that INPDS will operate by using a pre-programmed list of known phishing threat features and their indicators of compromise (IOCs). As a signature based-IDS it will monitor the packets traversing the network then compares these packets to the database of known IOCs or attack signatures to flag any suspicious behavior.

Designing an efficient and applicable vetting system that identifies malicious domains in real-time is of paramount importance. To this end, we provide a scheme of our proposed deployment model that predicts the label of a domain in real-time through a real-time detection server (figure 7) inspired by the article in [19]. First, the user submits a domain to the web client. The request is forwarded to the real-time server where an HTTP request is sent to the domain, the associated DNS packets are captured, and 22 features (**currently**) are derived from the packets. Then, the trained model predicts the category of the domain and returns the prediction. [19].

Figure 8 - Design sketch based on [19] for INPDS

Works similar to anti-virus software. It employs a signature (pattern that correspond to a known threat) database of know attacks, and if a successful match with current input, an alert is raised. A well-known example of this type is Snort which is an open source IDS that monitors network by matching each packet it observes against a set of rules of the DNS message in a specific packet window. Then, for each captured domain, we extract the lexical and third party features. As for the second phase of the design, also inspired by article [19] the new arrived data samples will be reported to the offline server which holds a copy of the ML model. The offline server needs to work with data streams and thus it applies incremental learning and hyper parameter optimization. In the scheme, incremental learning realizes by re-training the same model and tunes it according to new arrival data samples. Since incremental learning learns each new data sample individually, the whole process requires low computational cost. In the last step, the classifier and dataset residing on a real-time detection server are updated accordingly to serve coming data streams in the future.

Figure 9- Taxonomy of an IDS System

Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDSs) are widely-deployed security tools for detecting cyber-attacks and activities conducted by intruders for observing network traffics. With the increase in network speed and number and types of attacks, existing NIDSs, face challenges of capturing every packet to compare them to malicious signatures. These challenges will impact on the efficiency of NIDSs, mainly the performance and accuracy power. Throughout the analysis of the literature on this topic, the article in [20] found that the Packet-based NIDSs process every packet (payload) received. While it produces low false alarms, it is very time consuming, therefore it is hard, to perform packet-based approach at the speed of multiple Gigabits per second (Gbps). Flow-based NIDSs have an overall lower amount of data to be process, therefore it is the logical choice for high speed networks but it suffers from producing high false alarms [20]. Therefore, it can be recommended that, a hybrid or a mixture model of both NIDSs may ensure a higher ability to react on the wider scope of attacks within the high-speed networks environment, using packet-based phishing detection system for HTTP /HTTPs protocol is only my side of the project where my other research colleagues are working on flow-based IDS and other types of attacks.

Figure 10 - Packet-Based NIDS

Figure 11 - Flow-Based NIDS

1. Features Extraction:

The following is an in depth analysis of each feature currently used for our INPDS model ([For further information, examine the implemented computer code in \[26\]](#)):

1.1 Lexical features

Lexical features help detect malicious domain names since attackers apply different typo squatting and obfuscation methods to mimic the real domain names. In this research, we have extracted 11 features from each domain elaborated as follows:

Subdomain: Most malicious domains have few subdomains to mimic the real domain. For instance, to mimic `www.facebook.com`, the malicious domain could be in the format of `www.facebook.f.com`. In this case, the Top-Level Domain (TLD) is `f` and not `facebook`. However, people without enough background knowledge may be deceived.

They give the example of the following link: <http://www.hud.ac.uk/students/>. A domain name might include the country-code top-level domains (ccTLD), which in this example is “uk”. The “ac” part is shorthand for “academic”, *the combined “ac.uk” is called a second-level domain (SLD)* and “hud” is the actual name of the domain.

To produce this rule for extracting this feature:

First we had to omit the (`www.`) from the URL which is in fact a sub domain in itself.

Then, they removed the (ccTLD) i.e : country-code and top-level domains if it exists.

Finally, they counted the remaining dots in the URL.

If the number of dots is greater than one,

then the URL is classified as “**Suspicious**” since it has one sub domain.

However, if the dots are greater than two, it is classified as “**Phishing**” since it will have multiple sub domains.

Otherwise, if the URL has no sub domains, we assign “**Legitimate**” to the feature.

--By the end on the analysis we concluded the following rule:

$$\text{Rule: IF } \begin{cases} \text{Dots In Domain Part} = 1 \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \\ \text{Dots In Domain Part} = 2 \rightarrow \text{Suspicious} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \end{cases}$$

Top-Level Domain (TLD): Based on the previous studies, most malicious domains are with specific TLDs for a long duration of time, such as .com, .pw, to name a few. The possibility of a URL being malicious is higher when its TLD historically has been used for phishing URLs.

Second-Level Domain (SLD): SLD is the most critical part of a domain. Extracting features from SLD can help us get more information regarding the organization that registered the domain name. For example, in www.facebook.com, facebook is the SLD.

Length: The length of the domain consists of SLD and subdomains. Because phishing URLs or malicious domains are lengthy based on the previously discovered malicious URLs, considering the length feature is necessary.

Numeric percentage: This feature indicates the percentage of numerical characters to the length of the domain.

Entropy: This feature is based on the letter distribution and Shannon's entropy formula. ([For further information, examine the implemented computer code in \[26\]](#))

$$p = \frac{\text{letter_distribution}}{\text{domain_length}}, \text{Entropy} = \sum_{\text{letter}_i} p_i \times \log_2 p_i$$

N-gram: This feature extracts the uni-gram, bi-gram, and tri-gram of the domain at the character level. (*1-gram, 2-gram, 3-gram*)

Distance from bad words: There is a blacklist of all suspicious and harmful words. After tokenizing the domain to meaningful words, we get the average in distance of the domain's words from the blacklist.

Obfuscation method: To the best of our study, we considered nine different ways by which each domain can be obfuscated. If any of the following methods have been applied by the attacker, we mark the domain name as obfuscated:

1. existing @ in Domain:

This rule Using “@” symbol in the domain leads the browser to ignore everything preceding the “@” symbol and the real address often follows the “@” symbol.

Rule: IF $\begin{cases} \text{Url Having @ Symbol} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{cases}$

2. IP obfuscation Decimal 8 bits,
3. IP obfuscation Decimal 32 bits,
4. detecting IDN: suspicious domain name may be encoded with Unicode or international domain names encoded with Punycode, and
5. Shortened URLs: to confirm if it has been shortened or not, we send a request to see if it gets redirected to the real URL or not
6. Using Non-Standard Port :

This feature is useful in validating if a particular service (e.g. HTTP) is up or down on a specific server. In the aim of controlling intrusions, it is much better to merely open ports that you need. Several firewalls, Proxy and Network Address Translation (NAT) servers will, by default, block all or most of the ports and only open the ones selected. If all ports are open, phishers can run almost any service they want and as a result, user information is threatened. The most important ports and their preferred status are shown in Table 2. i.e (*port 80 and 443 are the only ports that should be open*)

We concluded the following rule to extract this future:

Rule: IF $\begin{cases} \text{Port \# is of the Preferred Status} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{cases}$

Table of Common ports to be checked

<i>PORT</i>	<i>Service</i>	<i>Meaning</i>	<i>Preferred Status</i>
21	FTP	Transfer files from one host to another	Close
22	SSH	Secure File Transfer Protocol	Close
23	Telnet	provide a bidirectional interactive text-oriented communication	Close
80	HTTP	Hyper text transfer protocol	Open
443	HTTPS	Hypertext transfer protocol secured	Open
445	SMB	Providing shared access to files, printers, serial ports	Close
1433	MSSQL	Store and retrieve data as requested by other software applications	Close
1521	ORACLE	Access oracle database from web.	Close
3306	MySQL	Access MySQL database from web.	Close
3389	Remote Desktop	allow remote access and remote collaboration	Close

7. Adding Prefix or Suffix Separated by (-) to the Domain:

The researchers also concluded from the datasets in paper [13] that a dash symbol is rarely used in legitimate URLs. Phishers tend to add prefixes or suffixes separated by (-) to the domain name so that users feel that they are dealing with a legitimate webpage. For example <http://www.Confirme-paypal.com/>. So they suggested the following rule:

Rule: IF $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Domain Name Part Includes (-)Symbol} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{array} \right.$

```
[76]: df_test.info()
```

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>  
RangeIndex: 2126 entries, 0 to 2125  
Data columns (total 21 columns):  
#   Column                Non-Null Count  Dtype  
---  ---  
0   Country                2076 non-null   string  
1   IP                     2126 non-null   string  
2   IP                     2126 non-null   string  
3   Domain                 2126 non-null   string  
4   subdomain              2126 non-null   float64  
5   obfuscate_at_sign      2126 non-null   float64  
6   numeric_percentage     2126 non-null   float64  
7   Registrant_Name        2126 non-null   string  
8   Domain_Age             2126 non-null   string  
9   Emails                 2126 non-null   string  
10  Organization            0 non-null      string  
11  Name_Server_Count      2126 non-null   float64  
12  Creation_Date_Time     2126 non-null   string  
13  Alexa_Rank             2116 non-null   float64  
14  len                    2126 non-null   int64  
15  lgram                  2126 non-null   string  
16  entropy                2126 non-null   float64  
17  tld                    2126 non-null   string  
18  3gram                  2126 non-null   string  
19  2gram                  2126 non-null   string  
20  label                  2126 non-null   float64  
dtypes: float64(7), int64(1), string(13)  
memory usage: 348.9 KB
```

1.2 Third party features

The third party features are extracted from two third party sources, i.e., Whois and Alexa rank and they contain the biographical properties of a domain. In [19] researchers have gone through feature evaluation using information gain analysis to get the merits of each feature in each category, applying the feature selection algorithm in Weka, i.e., *InfoGainAttributeEval*, to obtain the top 13 features, out of the underlying dataset.

Proving the third party features as the most influential one among the top 13 features.

Rank	Average Merit	Feature
1	0.227 +- 0	Registrant Name
2	0.216 +- 0	Organization
3	0.213 +- 0	Country
4	0.212 +- 0	Emails
5	0.211 +- 0	State
6	0.205 +- 0	TLD
7	0.196 +- 0	Registrar
8	0.194 +- 0	Domain Name
9	0.192 +- 0.005	TTL Variance
10	0.182 +- 0.004	TTL Mean
11	0.18 +- 0	SLD
12	0.161 +- 0	Unique ASN
13	0.155 +- 0.001	Longest word

Figure 12 - FEATURE AVERAGE MERIT

a) **Domain Registration:**

Phishing website lives for a short period of time, so they suggest that trustworthy domains are regularly paid for several years in advance. In their dataset analysis, they found that the longest fraudulent domains have been used for one year only.

Rule: IF { Domains Expires on \leq 1 years \rightarrow Phishing
Otherwise \rightarrow Legitimate

b) Age of Domain:

This feature can be extracted from WHOIS database (Whois 2005). *Most phishing websites live for a short period of time.* By reviewing the paper's [14] dataset, the authors found that the minimum age of the legitimate domain is 6 months.

Rule: IF $\begin{cases} \text{Age Of Domain} \geq 6 \text{ months} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \end{cases}$

c) DNS Record:

For phishing websites, either the claimed identity is not recognized by the WHOIS database (Whois 2005) or no records founded for the hostname (Pan and Ding 2006).

If the DNS record is **empty** or not found then the website is classified as “**Phishing**”,
Otherwise it is classified as “**Legitimate**”.

Rule: IF $\begin{cases} \text{no DNS Record For The Domain} \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{cases}$

d) Website Traffic:

This feature measures the popularity of the website by determining the number of visitors and the number of pages they visit. However, *since phishing websites live for a short period of time, they may not be recognized by the Alexa database (Alexa the Web Information Company., 1996).*

By reviewing their dataset in article [13], they found that in worst scenarios, legitimate websites ranked among the top 100,000. Furthermore,

if the domain has no traffic or is not recognized by the Alexa database, it is classified as “Phishing”.

Otherwise, it is classified as “**Suspicious**”

Rule: IF $\begin{cases} \text{Website Rank} < 100,000 \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \\ \text{Website Rank} > 100,000 \rightarrow \text{Suspicious} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Phish} \end{cases}$

1.4.1. PageRank

PageRank is a value ranging from “0” to “1”. PageRank aims to measure how important a webpage is on the Internet. The greater the PageRank value the more important the webpage. In the datasets, *they found that about 95% of phishing webpages have no PageRank*. Moreover, the remaining 5% of phishing webpages may reach a PageRank value up to “0.2”.

Rule: IF $\begin{cases} \text{PageRank} < 0.2 \rightarrow \text{Phishing} \\ \text{Otherwise} \rightarrow \text{Legitimate} \end{cases}$

Table 1: List of the final 22 DNS-based features.

Feature	Feature name	Description
Lexical		
F1	Subdomain	Has sub-domain or not
F2	TLD	Top-level domain
F3	SLD	Second-level domain
F4	Len	Length of domain and subdomain
F5	Numeric percentage	Counts the number of digits in domain and subdomain
F6	Entropy	Entropy of letter distribution
F7	1-gram	1-gram of the domain in letter level

F8	2-gram	2-gram of the domain in letter level
F9	3-gram	3-gram of the domain in letter level
F10	Distance from bad words	Computes average distance from bad words
F11	Obfuscation	Max value for URL obfuscation
Third party		
F12	Domain name	Name of the domain
F13	Registrar	Registrar of the domain
F14	Registrant name	The name the domain has been registered
F15	Creation date time	The date and time the domain created
F16	Emails	The emails associated to a domain
F17	Domain age	The age of a domain
F18	Organization	What organization it is linked to
F19	State	The state the main branch is

F20 Country The country the main branch is

F21 Name server count The total number of name servers linked to the domain

F22 Alexa rank The rank of the domain by Alexa

D. Data Collection

1. Train Dataset: CIC-Bell-DNS 2021

In this research work [19] [18] they generated and released a large DNS features dataset of 400,000 benign and 13,011 malicious samples processed from a million benign and 51,453 known-malicious domains from publicly available datasets. The malicious samples span between three categories of spam, phishing, and malware. The dataset, namely CIC-Bell-DNS2021 replicates the real-world scenarios with frequent benign traffic and diverse malicious domain types.

One of the contributions of this research is to generate a large DNS features dataset based on the malicious and benign domains. As explained earlier, they sent HTTP requests to the gathered domains and the associated packets were captured. Then the captured packets were pre-processed, and the proposed features were extracted from the packets using a developed DNS-based feature extractor. Finally, the features were post-processed to create the final dataset. They managed to collect more than one million domains from various sources falling under four different categories of malware, spam, phishing, and benign domains. All the domains have been collected *between May 2019 to June 2019* and later updated with domains from **December 2020 for further validation**.

Each domain category is briefly explained as follows:

Malware domains

Malware category refers to the domains that have been previously identified to generate any general type of malware including drive-by download, DGA-based botnets, Distributed

Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, and spyware. The malware domains were collected from DNS-BH [19] and malware domain list [20].

Spam domains

Spammers employ different ways to find valid email addresses for sending bulk emails. Dictionary harvest attack is one of the common ways to seek a valid email address by randomly sending mail to widely used mailbox names for a domain.

Phishing domains

Phishing domains imitate the looks of legitimate websites and leverage social engineering techniques to trick users into clicking the malicious link. Upon clicking the fake link through email or SMS, the user is directed to an imposter website asking for the user's login credentials and private information. In the dataset, the phishing domains were collected from OpenPhish [17] and PhishTank [18] which are collaborative phishing verification websites where the users submit the phishing data, and the community users vote for it.

Benign domains

All the domains that are not in the above categories are deemed to be benign. They gathered all benign domains from Majestic Million [16]. Table below shows the breakdown of the dataset in terms of the number of collected domains (original domain) in each category of malware, spam, phishing, and benign. After sending HTTP requests to each domain, some of the domains do not respond, e.g., C&C servers that are not alive anymore. The remaining domains that **respond OK (200)** are logged and, associated DNS packets are dumped. In Table below, the domains and packets that have been successfully processed are identified with columns “domains processed” and “packets processed”, respectively. [18] *As four our research project we only took phishing and benign CSV files and combined them to generate a training datasets.*

Category	Original domains	Domains processed	Packets processed
Malware	26,895	9,432	182,266
Spam	8,254	1,976	61,046
Phishing	16,307	12,586	95,492
Benign	988,667	500,000	6,907,719

Figure 13 - Statistics of the domains dataset

	Country	ASN	TTL	IP	Domain	State	Registrant_Name	Country.1	Creation_Date_Time
500237	US	14888.0	3599	204.58.233.127	www.lnbo.com	NE		US	1994-12-01 05:00:00
500238	BG	210250.0	3599	194.1.147.89	iqsurvey.com	Panama		PA	1999-11-22 05:22:33
500239	BG	210250.0	3598	194.1.147.89	iqsurvey.com	Panama		PA	1999-11-22 05:22:33
500240	BG	210250.0	3599	194.1.147.89	www.iqsurvey.com	Panama		PA	1999-11-22 05:22:33
500241	US	14618.0	299	35.168.216.102	maciverinstitute.com	Washington		US	2008-12-30 01:49:00
500242	US	14618.0	3599	35.168.216.102	www.maciverinstitute...	Washington		US	2008-12-30 01:49:00
500243			3599		www.maciverinstitute...	Washington		US	2008-12-30 01:49:00
500244	CA	13335.0	3599	23.227.38.32	blinkforhome.com	MA		US	2014-06-23 03:11:55
500245	CA	13335.0	2418	23.227.38.32	blinkforhome.com	MA		US	2014-06-23 03:11:55
500246	US	13335.0	119	104.28.26.27	fiercegovernmentit.com	State		US	2008-11-13 18:29:19
500247			119		fiercegovernmentit.com	State		US	2008-11-13 18:29:19
500248	US	13335.0	3599	104.17.70.206	pages.questexweb.com	Arizona		US	2015-01-30 21:43:37
500249			3599		pages.questexweb.com				2015-01-30 21:43:37
500250	US	14618.0	299	54.227.241.240	www.questex.com	Massachusetts		US	2002-07-29 20:42:57
500251	US	13335.0	299	104.31.84.253	rossdawson.com	New South Wales		AU	2006-02-05 02:21:21
500252			299		rossdawson.com	New South Wales		AU	2006-02-05 02:21:21
500253	US	13335.0	299	104.31.85.253	rossdawson.com	New South Wales		AU	2006-02-05 02:21:21
500254			298		rossdawson.com	New South Wales		AU	2006-02-05 02:21:21
500255	DE	8560.0	3599	217.160.0.178	weddingprime.de				
500256			3599		weddingprime.de				
500257	UA	24703.0	21599	195.128.17.206	viasenko.net	--		UA	2000-10-16 13:58:43
500258	AU	24446.0	14399	202.47.4.14	diterrencescamp.com...				

Figure 14- Processed Training Dataset CSV file contains 5012 586 row of benign and phishing Domains and their features

2. Test Dataset: real time based scenario

Fig.15. describes all the steps involved in the test dataset generation process which will play the role of real time packet transfer scenario; Starting with downloading the URLs data CSV files containing phishing and legitimate URLs, then transferring it into a PCAP file using a python sniffer called Passer that can work off a live packet capture. The next step is extracting HTTP and DNS lookup logs from this PCAP file so we can enrich the sets with other columns that will be useful in the feature extraction phase (same 22 DNS-based features as the CIC BELL training dataset) and finally fitting it into a Machine Learning model.

Figure 15- Design for generating synthetic test datasets that represent a real time packet flow scenario

Based on the research design in **figure 15**. And the sections these are the major steps involved in the data collection phase for the testing data:

Data Preprocessing: removed nulls and duplicate records since they affect our Machine Learning (ML) model. Also, removed unnecessary columns and retained only URL and Label columns.

WOIS Verification: the preprocessed data was split into benign sample set and malicious sample set. These two sample sets were individually checked for reachability of Whois to ensure our features data is not filled with meaningless features. I also checked from blacklist sites and phish tank if the Urls are malicious or begins to avoid throwing ML model off balance as well as Big Data domain.

Verified CSV file: the Whois and black site API verified benign and malicious URLs were further sampled to 5000 URLs each and merged to get a final dataset for extracting features in *data.csv* with 10 000 Urls.

Generating PCAP file: I first had to create a python code that can insert the 10 000 Urls from the *data.csv* file into a list then with a FOR loop I open connexion to each URL. ([For further information, examine the implemented python code in \[26\]](#))


```

netinspector.py x  urllibRequestURLs.py x  passer.py x
20 import ssl
21 import OpenSSL
22 import logging
23 from celery.app.log import Logging
24
25 # Load Datasets
26 def loadDataset(file_name):
27     df = pd.read_csv(file_name)
28     return df
29
30 df_URLs = loadDataset("URLs.csv")
31
32 List = df_URLs['url']
33
34 length = len(List)
35 for url in List:
36     print(url)
37
38     try:
39         request = urllib.Request(url)
40         request.add_header('User-Agent', 'Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/77.0.3865.120 Safari/537.36')
41         response = urllib.urlopen(request)
42         rdata = response.info()
43         ipaddr = socket.gethostbyname(request.origin_req_host)
44     except Exception as e:
45         print(logging.traceback.format_exc())

```

Figure 16- URlibRequest.py source code to open connexion to the List of URLs

Then I launched the python3 code in a kali linux terminal to open the connexions.

```

khaoula@kali: ~/Desktop
File Actions Edit View Help

return opener.open(url, data, timeout)
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 523, in open
response = meth(req, response)
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 632, in http_response
response = self.parent.error(
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 555, in error
result = self._call_chain(*args)
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 494, in _call_chain
result = func(*args)
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 747, in http_error_302
return self.parent.open(new, timeout=req.timeout)
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 517, in open
response = self._open(req, data)
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 534, in _open
result = self._call_chain(self.handle_open, protocol, protocol +
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 494, in _call_chain
result = func(*args)
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 1389, in https_open
return self.do_open(http.client.HTTPSConnection, req,
File "/usr/lib/python3.9/urllib/request.py", line 1349, in do_open
raise URLError(err)
urllib.error.URLError: <urlopen error [SSL: CERTIFICATE_VERIFY_FAILED] certifica
te verify failed: Hostname mismatch, certificate is not valid for 'us.imdb.com'.
(_ssl.c:1129)>

http://efilmcritic.com/hbs.cgi?movie=311
http://christian.net/
http://www.indsource.com
http://www.greatestescapes.com
http://hhalter.tripod.com/

```

Figure 17- Outputs of the URlibrequet.py in kali linux terminal

Using Wireshark in Kali Linux and a python sniffer called Passer that can work off a live packet capture from the other python code I launched in terminal 1, then generated the PCAP file.

The image shows two windows side-by-side. The left window is Wireshark, displaying a packet capture on the interface eth0. The packet list pane shows several DNS and TCP packets. The packet details pane for the selected packet shows it is an Internet Protocol Version 4 packet from 10.0.2.15 to 10.1.27.100. The packet bytes pane shows the raw data in hexadecimal and ASCII. The right window is a terminal window showing the execution of a python script. The terminal output shows the script successfully opening connections to various websites, including http://members.tripod.com/russiastation/.

Figure 18- The outputs of Wireshark and passer.py in terminal 2

Figure 19- Wireshark Packet capture outputs of the 10 000 url connexions

The outputs of both terminals can be viewed in the following Screenshot:

Figure 20- terminals outputs for passer.py and urllibrequest.py

Generating DNS and HTTP logs: using **SCAPY** and **DPKT** libraries in python to parse a PCAP file and the packets within it.

I created a tool that reads the raw PCAP file, parses and decodes the Ethernet, IP, TCP, and HTTP layers, and prints out the URI of the HTTP requests by using a PCAP object that listens to the network and returns a packet object when it hears a packet go by. [26]

Then generated *DNS_logs.csv* and *HTTP_logs.csv* that will be helpful in extracting features.

ID_packet	IP_src	UDP_sport	IP_dst	UDP_dport	DNS_id	Domaine	DNS_qr	DNS_qd	DNS_qdtype	type_table	
0	2	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	47533	47210	ecnavi.jp	1	[Q(name='ecnavi.jp', type=28)]	28	AAAA
1	78	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	43722	7987	ecnavi.jp	1	[Q(name='ecnavi.jp')]	1	A
2	80	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	47296	30024	hubpages.com	1	[Q(name='hubpages.com')]	1	A
3	81	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	47296	54860	hubpages.com	1	[Q(name='hubpages.com', type=28)]	28	AAAA
4	98	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	55060	48426	discover.hubpages.com	1	[Q(name='discover.hubpages.com')]	1	A
...
2121	23221	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	34276	43676	c1781279.ferozo.com	1	[Q(name='c1781279.ferozo.com')]	1	A
2122	23222	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	33341	34713	c1781279.ferozo.com	1	[Q(name='c1781279.ferozo.com', type=28)]	28	AAAA
2123	23223	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	60738	44402	rusnod.ru	1	[Q(name='rusnod.ru')]	1	A
2124	23224	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	50988	30583	rusnod.ru	1	[Q(name='rusnod.ru', type=28)]	28	AAAA
2125	23230	192.168.8.1	53	10.0.2.15	46190	48473	rusnod.ru	1	[Q(name='rusnod.ru')]	1	A

2126 rows × 11 columns

Enriching the Testing dataset: after fusing the http and DNS logs into a single data frame I used pre-defined functions to enrich the datasets. At the end of this step we get our final *testing_data.csv* file that will be used to extract features and train our model to classify phishing attacks.

ID_packet	IP_src	Domain	subdomain	sum	obfuscate_at_sign	UDP_sport	numeric_percentage	IP	
603	11115	192.168.8.1	clien.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
604	11116	192.168.8.1	clien.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
605	11130	192.168.8.1	www.clien.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
606	11131	192.168.8.1	www.clien.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
607	11143	192.168.8.1	www.clien.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
608	11144	192.168.8.1	www.clien.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
609	11213	192.168.8.1	clien.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
610	11215	192.168.8.1	marvel.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
611	11216	192.168.8.1	marvel.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
612	11229	192.168.8.1	www.marvel.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
613	11230	192.168.8.1	www.marvel.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
614	11304	192.168.8.1	marvel.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
615	11306	192.168.8.1	eksisozluk.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
616	11307	192.168.8.1	eksisozluk.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
617	11377	192.168.8.1	eksisozluk.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
618	11379	192.168.8.1	oneplus.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
619	11380	192.168.8.1	oneplus.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
620	11395	192.168.8.1	www.oneplus.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
621	11396	192.168.8.1	www.oneplus.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
622	11406	192.168.8.1	www.oneplus.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
623	11407	192.168.8.1	www.oneplus.com	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15
624	11476	192.168.8.1	oneplus.net	0.0	0	0.0	53	0.0	10.0.2.15

Figure 21 - Resulted Testing Dataset with 2126 entries for benign and phishing Domain names and its 22 DNS-based extracted features

E. Models Implementation

We provide a methodology for feature engineering of packet captures. We developed 22 **(currently)** clearly defined discriminative features including lexical-based and third party-based (biographical) features based on the CIC BELL dataset [18]. First, the captured DNS PCAP file is read and all the domains in the answer section of type A, AAAA, and CNAME query responses are retained. The field “rrname” keeps the domain name. Meanwhile, the statistical features are extracted from the structure of the DNS message in a specific packet window. Then, for each captured domain, we extract the lexical and third party features.

The categorical features namely, sld, emails, domain name, country, registrar, state, registrant name, longest word, organization, tld are transformed and represented as continuous values. Average of n-gram frequencies, typos, and distance from bad words were computed. Also, creation date time and domain age are converted to seconds and years, respectively. **The rest of the numerical features remain unchanged.** Besides, we calculate the maximum value of the nine obfuscation methods and merge them all into **one feature of obfuscation**. Finally, we create a CSV file of all the post-processed features values. The third stage trains the ML model, and the fourth stage validates and evaluates the model using fold cross-validation. [\(For further information, examine the implemented computer code in \[26\]\)](#)

We used multiple machine learning algorithms namely:

1. Decision Tree

A decision tree is a supervised machine learning algorithm that can be used for both classification and regression problems. A decision tree is simply a series of sequential decisions made to reach a specific result. [21]

We Created the classifier, fit it on the training data and made predictions on the test set, we choosed **max_depth=3** as the depth of the tree known as a hyper parameter before we fit the model to the data.

Because my decision boundary is too complex, I can over fit the data, which means that my model will be describing noise as well as signal.

If the **max_depth** is too small, we might be under fitting the data, meaning that the model doesn't contain enough of the signal.

In the decision tree Python implementation of the scikit-learn library, this is made by the parameter 'criterion'. This parameter is the function used to measure the quality of a split and it allows users to choose between 'Gini 'or 'entropy'. The entropy is calculated using the following formula:

$$Entropy = - \sum_j p_j \cdot \log_2 \cdot p_j$$

Entropy is a measure of information that indicates the disorder of the features with the target. Similar to the Gini Index, the optimum split is chosen by the feature with less entropy. It gets its maximum value when the probability of the two classes is the same and a node is pure when the entropy has its minimum value, which is 0. . [26]

```
clf = DecisionTreeClassifier(class_weight=None, criterion='entropy', max_depth=3,
                             max_features=None, max_leaf_nodes=None,
                             min_impurity_decrease=0.0,
                             min_samples_leaf=1,
                             min_weight_fraction_leaf=0.0, random_state=None,
                             splitter='best')
```

```
#clf = DecisionTreeClassifier(criterion='entropy',max_depth=3,)
clf.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

```
DecisionTreeClassifier(criterion='entropy', max_depth=3)
```

```
#accuracy on Training dataset
clf.score(X_train,y_train)
```

```
0.9902798297470796
```

2. Random Forest

Random Forest is a tree-based machine learning algorithm that leverages the power of multiple decision trees for making decisions. It is a forest of randomly created decision trees.

Each node in the decision tree works on a random subset of features to calculate the output. The random forest then combines the output of individual decision trees to generate the final output. [21]

"Tree Ensembles" or Random Forest often have the best predictive accuracy with labeled, tabular data because trees can fit non-linear, non-monotonic relationships, and interactions between features.

A single decision tree, grown to unlimited depth, will over fit. We solved this problem by assembling trees, with bagging (Random Forest) because the latter may be less sensitive to hyper parameters. We also tested with not only One-hot encoding of categorical features for tree ensembles but also with arbitrary "ordinal" encoding (Randomly assigning an integer to each category.) Compared to one-hot encoding, the dimensionality was lower, and the predictive accuracy was the same and even slightly better. . [26]

```

pipeline = make_pipeline(
    ce.OneHotEncoder(use_cat_names='true'),
    SimpleImputer(strategy='constant'),
    RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=110, random_state=42, n_jobs=-1)
)

# fit on train, score on val
pipeline.fit(X_train, y_train)
print('Training accuracy', pipeline.score(X_train, y_train))
print('Validation accuracy', pipeline.score(X_test, y_test))

```

Training accuracy 0.9999360252060688
Validation accuracy 0.9999360252060688

In future work, to convert the categorical features into numeric attributes because we have variables with a high number of categorical levels, we are considering combining levels or using the hashing trick.

3. Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is the appropriate regression analysis to conduct when the dependent variable is dichotomous (binary). Like all regression analyses, logistic regression is a predictive analysis. Logistic regression is used to describe data and to explain the relationship between one dependent binary variable and one or more nominal, ordinal, interval or ratio-level independent variables. [22]

class_weight of LR works by penalizing mistakes in samples of class[i] with class_weight[i] instead of 1. So higher class-weight means you want to put more emphasis on a class. From what you say it seems class 0 is 19 times more frequent than class 1. So you should increase the class_weight of class 1 relative to class 0, say {0:.1, 1:.9}. If the class_weight doesn't sum to 1, it will basically change the regularization parameter.

For our model version we used `class_weight="balanced"` it basically means replicating the smaller class until we have as many samples as in the larger one, but in an implicit way. [26]

```

: from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
  logreg = LogisticRegression(class_weight='balanced')
  sd=logreg.fit(X_train,y_train)
  logreg.score(X_train,y_train),logreg.score(X_test,y_test)

```

4. K Nearest Neighbor (KNN)

KNN is an algorithm, based on the local minimum of the target function which is used to learn an unknown function of desired precision and accuracy. The algorithm also finds the neighborhood of an unknown input, its range or distance from it, and other parameters. It's based on the principle of "information gain"—the algorithm finds out which is most suitable to predict an unknown value. [23]

In KNN, there are a few hyper-parameters that we need to tune to get an optimal result. Among the various hyper-parameters that can be tuned to make the KNN algorithm more effective and reliable, the distance metric is one of the important ones through which we calculate the distance between the data points as for some applications certain distance metrics are more effective. There are many kinds of distance functions that can be used in KNN such as Euclidean Distance, Hamming distance, Minkowski distance, Kullback-Leiber (KL) divergence, BM25 etc.

Euclidean Distance, with the equation :

$$D_{euclidean}(x, y) = \|x - y\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^N |x - y|^2}$$

Minkowski Distance, with the equation :

$$D_{minkowski}(x, y) = \|x - y\|_\lambda = \sqrt[\lambda]{\sum_{j=1}^N |x - y|^\lambda}$$

Manhattan Distance with the equation ::

$$D_{manhattan}(x, y) = \|x - y\|_1 = \sum_{j=1}^N |x - y|$$

Chebyshev Distance with the equation ::

$$D_{chebyshev}(x, y) = \|x - y\|_\lambda = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt[\lambda]{\sum_{j=1}^N |x - y|^\lambda}$$

The description of the above equation is:

D = the result of the calculation of the distance of the x and y data.

N = the number of features in the dataset.

λ = the parameter used for the Minkowski distance.

Euclidean distance can be generalized using **Minkowski** norm also known as the p norm. The formula for Minkowski distance is:

$$D(x,y) = \sqrt[p]{\sum_d |x_d - y_d|^p}$$

Here we can see that the formula differs from the formula of Euclidean distance as we can see that instead of squaring the difference, we have raised the difference to the power of p and have also taken the p root of the difference. Now the biggest advantage of using such a distance metric is that we can change the value of p to get different types of distance metrics.

p = 2

If we take the value of p as 2 then we get the Euclidean distance. We also chooses to go with 5 as a number of neighbors to use by default for `kneighbors` queries.

```
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
classifier = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors = 5, metric = 'minkowski', p = 2);
```

```
classifier.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

```
KNeighborsClassifier()
```

```
X_test
```

```
array([[ -0.6944135 , -0.01025784, -0.2061333 , ..., -1.10324628,
        -1.73308783, -1.73231096],
       [ -0.6944135 , -0.01025784, -0.2061333 , ..., -1.28163046,
        -1.7315704 , -1.73078766],
       [ -0.6944135 , -0.01025784, -0.2061333 , ..., -1.28163046,
        -1.7315704 , -1.73078766],
       ...,
       [ -0.6944135 , -0.01025784, -0.2061333 , ..., -1.00414396,
        -1.72819139, -1.72739556],
       [ -0.6944135 , -0.01025784, -0.2061333 , ..., -1.00414396,
        -1.72819139, -1.72739556],
       [ -0.6944135 , -0.01025784, -0.2061333 , ..., -1.00414396,
        -1.72819139, -1.72739556]])
```

5. Multilayer Perceptron

Multilayer Perceptron has input and output layers, and one or more **hidden layers** with many neurons stacked together. And while in the Perceptron the neuron must have an activation function that imposes a threshold, like ReLU or sigmoid, neurons in a Multilayer Perceptron can use any arbitrary activation function. [24]

We created the MLP and activated it by means of ReLU so we can funnel the information into a very dense format. This way, the model will be capable of learning the most important patterns, which helps generalizing to new data.

Finally, there's an output layer, which has num_classes output neurons and activates by means of Softmax. The number of neurons equals the number of scalars in our output vector. Since that data must be categorical for categorical cross entropy, and thus the number of scalar values in our target vector equals the number of classes, it makes sense why num_classes is used. Softmax, the activation function, is capable of generating a so-called multiclass probability distribution. That is, it computes the probability that a certain feature vector belongs to one class. We just configured the model architecture.

So the model can learn we configure the following hyper parameters:

We use categorical cross entropy as our loss function and the Adam optimizer for optimizing our model. It combines various improvements to traditional stochastic gradient descent (Kingman and Ba, 2014; Ruder, 2016). Adam is the standard optimizer used today. Accuracy is highly intuitive to humans so we'll use that alongside our categorical cross entropy loss. Next, we fit the training data to our model. We choose 10 epochs, or the number of iterations before it stops training, a batch size of 250, verbosity mode 1 and a validation split of 20% [26].

6. Gaussian Naive Bayes

Naive Bayes Classifiers are based on the Bayes Theorem. One assumption taken is the strong independence assumptions between the features. These classifiers assume that the value of a particular feature is independent of the value of any other feature. In a supervised learning situation, Naive Bayes Classifiers are trained very efficiently. [25]

The Formula For Bayes' Theorem Is

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(B)} = \frac{P(A) \cdot P(B|A)}{P(B)}$$

where:

$P(A)$ = The probability of A occurring

$P(B)$ = The probability of B occurring

$P(A|B)$ = The probability of A given B

$P(B|A)$ = The probability of B given A

$P(A \cap B)$ = The probability of both A and B occurring

F. Preliminary Results and Analysis

7. Numerical Features

We train and validate the classification models focusing on numerical features in the first analysis:

7.1 Decision Tree

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.39	1.00	0.56	822
Phishing 1	0.00	0.00	0.00	1303
accuracy			0.39	2125
macro avg	0.19	0.50	0.28	2125
weighted avg	0.15	0.39	0.22	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[822 0]
[1303 0]]

Decision Tree Output view:

7.2 Random Forest

Top 20 numeric features table:

Random forest Output view:

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.39	1.00	0.56	822
Phishing 1	0.00	0.00	0.00	1303
accuracy			0.39	2125
macro avg	0.19	0.50	0.28	2125
weighted avg	0.15	0.39	0.22	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[822 0]
[1303 0]]

7.3 Logistic regression

Visualizing the y_{test} , y_{pred} results:

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.99	0.96	0.98	822
Phishing 1	0.98	1.00	0.99	1303
accuracy			0.98	2125
macro avg	0.99	0.98	0.98	2125
weighted avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[790 32]
[4 1299]]

7.4 KNN

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.47	0.99	0.64	822
Phishing 1	0.99	0.29	0.45	1303
accuracy			0.56	2125
macro avg	0.73	0.64	0.54	2125
weighted avg	0.79	0.56	0.52	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization

```
[[817  5]
 [927 376]]
```

```
C:\Users\PC1\AppData\Local\Temp\ipykernel_1800\17
ll be removed two minor releases later; please ca
plt.colorbar()
```


7.5 MLP

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.00	0.00	0.00	822
Phishing 1	0.61	1.00	0.76	1303
accuracy			0.61	2125
macro avg	0.31	0.50	0.38	2125
weighted avg	0.38	0.61	0.47	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization

```
[[ 0 822]
 [ 0 1303]]
```


7.6 GNB

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.39	1.00	0.56	822
Phishing 1	0.00	0.00	0.00	1303
accuracy			0.39	2125
macro avg	0.19	0.50	0.28	2125
weighted avg	0.15	0.39	0.22	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization

```
[[ 822  0]
 [1303  0]]
```

```
C:\Users\PC1\AppData\Local\Temp\ipykernel_1800\111
ll be removed two minor releases later; please c
plt.colorbar()
```


In the analysis step, we applied a set of machine learning algorithms on two subdivisions of the dataset, namely balanced and imbalanced.

We compare the classification results of multiple machine learning algorithms as seen in pervious sections showing the classification report and confusion matrix of each model. We used stratified 5-fold cross validation from the sklearn library which returns stratified folds for training and testing data by preserving the percentage of samples for each class. We shuffle each class's samples before splitting into train and test bins. As illustrated Logistic regression (LR) significantly outperforms k-NN, MLP, GNB,RF,DT and in terms of accuracy, f1-score, and precision It achieves 98% and 99% For 97/3% data ratio, the gaps between classification results are trivial where Multilayer perceptron MLP ranks second among other classifiers with a notable difference (almost 37% lower for accuracy) from LR. Overall, the results on the imbalanced dataset are superior to ones on the balanced dataset due to a higher ratio of benign samples that might influence the average classification measures. However, since we have used stratified sampling, we can make sure we have provided more uniformity during training by removing the variance of the proportions inside bins.

8. Categorical and numerical Features

We train and validate the classification models focusing now on both encoded categorical and numerical features in the second analysis:

Figure 22 - Soft and Hard conversions of categorical features used in our models next to One-hot encoder

8.1 Decision Tree

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.39	0.99	0.56	822
Phishing 1	0.73	0.01	0.03	1303
accuracy			0.39	2125
macro avg	0.56	0.50	0.29	2125
weighted avg	0.60	0.39	0.23	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[815 7]
[1284 19]]

8.2 Random Forest

Random forest Output view:

Top 20 features table:

Academic year: 2021-2022

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.39	1.00	0.56	822
Phishing 1	0.00	0.00	0.00	1303
accuracy			0.39	2125
macro avg	0.19	0.50	0.28	2125
weighted avg	0.15	0.39	0.22	2125

Confusion Matrix:

8.3 Logistic regression

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.45	0.68	0.55	822
Phishing 1	0.71	0.48	0.57	1303
accuracy			0.56	2125
macro avg	0.58	0.58	0.56	2125
weighted avg	0.61	0.56	0.56	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization
[[563 259]
[676 627]]

8.4 KNN

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.39	1.00	0.56	822
Phishing 1	0.00	0.00	0.00	1303
accuracy			0.39	2125
macro avg	0.19	0.50	0.28	2125
weighted avg	0.15	0.39	0.22	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization

```
[[ 822  0]
 [1303  0]]
```


8.5 MLP

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.00	0.00	0.00	822
Phishing 1	0.61	1.00	0.76	1303
accuracy			0.61	2125
macro avg	0.31	0.50	0.38	2125
weighted avg	0.38	0.61	0.47	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization

```
[[ 0 822]
 [ 0 1303]]
```


8.6 GNB

Classification report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Benign 0	0.39	1.00	0.56	822
Phishing 1	0.00	0.00	0.00	1303
accuracy			0.39	2125
macro avg	0.19	0.50	0.28	2125
weighted avg	0.15	0.39	0.22	2125

Confusion Matrix:

Confusion matrix, without normalization

```
[[ 822  0]
 [1303  0]]
```


In the second analysis, we compare the classification results of multiple machine learning algorithms focusing now on both encoded categorical and numerical features as seen in pervious sections showing the classification report and confusion matrix of each model. As illustrated , now Multilayer perceptron (MLP) significantly outperforms k-NN, LR, GNB,RF,DT in terms of accuracy, f1-score, and precision It achieves 61% and 76% For 97/3% data ratio, the gaps between classification results are trivial where Logistic regression (LR) ranks second among other classifiers with a notable difference (almost 05 % lower for accuracy) from MLP.

Overall, we noticed the results on the numeric features are superior to the ones with encoded categorical features because we need to find the right distance function that works for our dataset. The use of binary indicator variables solves this problem implicitly. This has the benefit of allowing us to continue our probably matrix based implementation with this kind of data, but a much simpler way - and appropriate for most distance based methods - is to just use a modified distance function which will be our future work to increase the accuracy rate.

There is an infinite number of such combinations. We need to experiment which works best for our case. Essentially, we might want to use some classic metric on the numeric values (usually with normalization applied; but it may make sense to also move this normalization into the distance function), plus a distance on the other attributes, scaled appropriately.

In most real application domains of distance based algorithms, this is the most difficult part, optimizing our domain specific distance function.

G. Conclusion and Future Work

In this research, we proposed an applicable phishing domain classification detection system based on lexical and third-party features acquired by deep inspection of DNS traffic. The proposed detection system achieves a somewhat promising preliminary results on several machine learning techniques. We also have shown that third-party features are the most important category of features in the classification process with a total 58% information gain among the top 13 features. We have worked on implementing a passive python network sniffer that capture live flow traffic and save it to a PCAP file so we can extract 22 features from 500,000 benign and 5,011 malicious DNS responses captured from over seven million DNS packets. In the future, we are planning to enrich our feature set by adding more state full /stateless features to add up to 35 features as well as orienting this INPDS system towards HTTPS protocol.

The existence of HTTPS is very important in giving the impression of website legitimacy, but this is clearly not enough. The authors in (Mohammad, Thabtah and McCluskey 2012) [14] (Mohammad, Thabtah and McCluskey 2013) [15] suggest checking the certificate assigned with HTTPS including the extent of the trust certificate issuer, and the certificate age. Certificate Authorities that are consistently listed among the top trustworthy names include: “GeoTrust, GoDaddy, Network Solutions, Thawte, Comodo, Doster and VeriSign”. Furthermore, by testing out the datasets in paper [13], they found that the minimum age of a reputable certificate is two years.

Rule: IF {
 Use https and Issuer Is Trusted and Age of Certificate \geq 1 Years \rightarrow Legitimate
 Using https and Issuer Is Not Trusted \rightarrow Suspicious
 Otherwise \rightarrow Phishing

And like the model approach in [16] we want to detect malicious HTTPS traffic without decryption in future work. To detect malicious HTTPS traffic, the authors analysed the different log files generated by *Bro IDS (Now renamed Zeek)* which provide comprehensive information about HTTPS traffic. They also used XGBoost machine learning algorithm to classify the traffic. The features are based on three different log files: - conn.log, ssl.log, and x509.log. They define their feature model by analysing the logs generated by Bro/Zeek; these logs provide detailed information about HTTPS traffic.

In general Bro generates different kinds of log files as follows:

- **conn.log:** TCP/UDP/ICMP connections
- **ssl.log:** A record of SSL sessions, including certificates being used.

- **x509.log:** X.509 certificates information.
- **http.log:** All HTTP requests with their replies.
- **Smtplib.log:** a description of SMTP activity.
- **ftp.log:** A log of FTP session activity.
- **dns.log:** DNS queries with their responses.
- **dpd.log:** A summary of protocols used on non-standard ports.
- **files.log:** Description of files transferred over the network and all the information collected from different protocols.

For the next step we want to extract the following:

1. SSL record: The **ssl.log** file provides information about SSL/TLS handshakes and encryption establishment process. It contains versions of SSL/TLS, server names, ciphers used, certificate path, subjects and issuer.

ssl.log

orig_h	id.orig_p	id.resp_h	id.resp_p	version	cipher	curve	server_name	resumed	last_alert	next_protocol	established	cert	chain	full
ing	addr	addr	port	string	string	string	bool	string	string	bool	vector(string)	vector(string)	string	st
CSeVRKJDIe2K5LFv14	147.32.84.59	38661	217.77.163.138	443	SSLv3		TLS_RSA_WITH_RC4_128_SHA	-	-	T	-	-	-	-
CXaT6T1M9Q3a2hlpY	147.32.84.59	39050	74.125.232.214	443	TLSv10		TLS_RSA_WITH_RC4_128_SHA	-	-	F	-	-	I	F3LzKQ3xQHON6Ks64k
CaHmID3kkWgfjTuY34	147.32.84.59	39051	74.125.232.214	443	TLSv10		TLS_RSA_WITH_RC4_128_SHA	-	-	F	-	-	I	FzAtC63h6JccbC0o1l
CGaw7e39Qzqqf2f7Qb	147.32.86.126	60835	89.185.253.133	443	-	-	-	-	-	F	-	-	F	-

2. Certificate record: The **x509.log** file contains the certificate record describing the information about certificate, such as certificate serial number, common names, time validities, subjects, certificate key length, etc

x509.log

1313419485.169830	FYoA52d171e7BnED9	3	4AF56A7BE6A0C025AB8C60B5AB40D73C	CN=*.dropbox.com,OU=IT,O=Dropbox\, Inc.,L=San l
1313419491.756879	F3LzKQ3xQHON6Ks64k	3	1F19F6DE35DD63A142918AD52CC0AB12	CN=mail.google.com,O=Google Inc,L=Mountain View,
1313419491.881272	FzAtC63h6JccbC0o1l	3	1F19F6DE35DD63A142918AD52CC0AB12	CN=mail.google.com,O=Google Inc,L=Mountain View,
1313419501.886237	FoUnnI2nNksJXq9KKg	3	4AF56A7BE6A0C025AB8C60B5AB40D73C	CN=*.dropbox.com,OU=IT,O=Dropbox\, Inc.,L=San l

3. Validation period of the certificates: The validity of a certificate can be checked by using the capture time and the validity period of the certificate. If the capture time is within the

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certificate validity period, then it is valid. The datatype of this feature (*R8*) is Boolean. If the certificate is valid, then the feature value is true, and the feature value is false if the certificate is not valid.

4. Number of domains in certificate SAN DNS: The SAN (Subject Alternative Names) describes which domains belong to this certificate. For example, a Google certificate SAN DNS is {*.google.com, *.google.ca, *.google.co.in, *.google.cl, *.google.co.uk, *.google.de}. For each new incoming certificate, the number of DNS in SAN is stored in a list. The average is calculated from the list.

In conclusion, the aim of the future research is to examine the HTTPS traffic PCAP file by extracting the elements previously highlighted in this work as well as other studies and deciding whether it is malicious or not. Connection information, SSL records, and certificate records will be used to extract the features. The connection will then be established depending on the source IP, destination IP, destination ports, and protocol. The output is labelled as either suspicious or normal. **This stage is still in progress** since we are presently working on HTTP traffic to figure out how we can identify the most critical **features that will not be encrypted during transfer**.

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Realized By *Khaoula Hidawi*
Under supervision of *Dr. Ismail Berrada*
**INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY
AND INNOVATION (IST&I)**
UM6P-CS